

The Impact of Organizational Integrity on Organizational Symmetry: An Analytical Study in the Public and Private Sectors

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to determine the effect of organizational Integrity, represented by the dimensions of (Optimism, Trust, Empathy, and Tolerance) on organizational Symmetry, represented by (Loyalty, Similarity, and Membership) in the public and private sectors in the KRI. Researchers used probability sampling to collect the data via a Google form (n = 144) using SPSS software V.26. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics to find the frequencies and percentages of the demographic questions. The Chi-Square Test was used to find the association relationship between variables; researchers used Spearman's rank-order correlation and regression analysis to show the correlation and the impact of organizational Integrity on organizational Symmetry. Results show no statistical relationship between demographic variables and respondents' opinions about how Integrity affected organizational Symmetry. A positive and significant correlation exists between organizational integrity and organizational Symmetry. In addition, results show that there is a statistically significant effect of organizational Integrity (Empathy and Tolerance) on organizational Symmetry (Loyalty and Similarity) and there is a statistically significant effect of one of the dimensions of organizational Integrity (Tolerance) on one of the dimensions of organizational Symmetry (Membership).

Keywords: Organizational Integrity, Organizational Symmetry, Optimism, Empathy, Trust, Tolerance, Loyalty, Similarity, and Membership.

1 INTRODUCTION

The Kurdistan region's Public and private sectors are important organizations responsible for society's growth and prosperity. their success depends on factors that contribute to and enhance their performance which requires loyalty, trust, and job Satisfaction. When it comes to the practical side of the study, public and private are both chosen, because principles and dimensions of (organizational integrity and symmetry) come from internal (inner) intentions, and that is why they can be implemented in both cases. These variables are not similar to other variables that require rules to follow or governmental necessities within the public sector, this is also true for the private sector. Organizational integrity principles lead to ethics, which is a moral virtue that raises the hopes, aspirations, and ambitions of working individuals, makes them more positive in their professional thinking and practices, more able to face contemporary challenges, and more determined to solve problems, it is one of the manifestations of organizational health, that focuses on spreading human behavior, establishing lofty practices, achieving individual and group affiliation and loyalty to it, leads to increasing their organizational commitment towards its goals. Top management needs organizational integrity to eliminate negative thinking among employees. Maintaining Integrity will increase the interest and trust of the employees in the organization, and lead to more informed decision-making, and effective resource allocation strategies. [1] On the other hand, organizational symmetry is considered a vital topic required in various public and private sectors. It has significant consequences and results that affect the performance and productivity of working individuals. It also affects the stability of employees, and the stability of the organization as a whole, and increases the chances of its progress. The higher the similarity of individuals with their organization, the better performance, loyalty, and job satisfaction. [2] Organizational Symmetry is affected by several influences that affect it directly or indirectly. One of these important influences is Organizational Integrity which is the element of influencing the behavior of working individuals and achieving the maximum benefit from their intellectual and practical abilities. Relying on it achieves the process of positive impact on the employee's behavior, and this provides an organizational climate in which a feeling of satisfaction, trust, Optimism, and Empathy among the individuals to achieve harmony and familiarity between working individuals to reach organizational symmetry, which according to [2] works on the psychological connection between employees as a work team and that their destiny and organization destiny became one, leading to increasing commitment, regularity, performance, and high motivation, reducing conflict and contradiction, increasing the degree of loyalty, and activating cooperation among the employees. Therefore, organizational symmetry has become an urgent necessity due to the developments witnessed in the administrative environment. It is considered an important indicator of workplace behavior, as the stronger the individual's Symmetry with their organization, the greater their motivation to act in behavior that enhances organizational success.

1.1 RESEARCH PROBLEM

Private and public sectors in Kurdistan need to improve their performance in managing administrative and organizational affairs due to the weakness of organizational integrity, and indicators in all their dimensions and contents. This weakness is reflected in performance levels due to the adoption of ineffective procedures in the field of work ethics, which hinders success in a volatile environment and leads to organizational crises. Therefore, attention must be paid to organizational symmetry, which has recently become a topic of wide interest among organizations seeking to achieve their goals, including ethical and humane principles based on trust and mutual respect. These principles encourage employees at all levels, enhance their well-being, and promote positive behaviors that improve performance and increase the effectiveness of sector outputs, as the search for the main reason for the poor performance stems from the lack of adoption of the dimensions of the organizational integrity, by the individuals in the sectors. The ambiguity of organizational integrity and its dimensions may negatively affect the achievement of organizational symmetry. Based on the above, the general framework of the study problem can be determined by the following intellectual questions:

1. To What extent did the investigated public and private sectors rely on Organizational Integrity?
2. What dimensions lead to the strongest relationship between organizational integrity and organizational Symmetry (collectively and individually)?
3. Does the sector's adoption of Organizational Integrity contribute to their Organizational Symmetry?

1.2 RESEARCH IMPORTANCE

1. The significance of the variables studied, both theoretically and practically, in the fields of organizational behavior and organizational theory, as the research contributes to enhancing administrative knowledge on topics that the local library lacks, such as organizational symmetry and organizational integrity, which are contemporary variables that attract significant attention from researchers.
2. The study derives its importance from its attempt to link these two main variables intellectually.

3. The study's philosophy revolves around analyzing the views of administrative leaders and employees in the sectors studied in the Kurdistan Region. The valuable ideas and opinions they provide, along with the findings and suggestions drawn from the study, will benefit these sectors in general.
4. The study focuses on the nature of the relationships and influences between the studied variables, which contributes positively to achieving the objectives of the sectors in the Kurdistan Region.

1.3 RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

Based on the problem of the study, the main objective of the study is focused on diagnosing and analyzing the relationships between the study variables at the administrative and employee levels of public and private sectors and their impact on each other, as well as the researchers trying to achieve the following goals:

1. Setting theoretical frameworks for the main and sub-study variables.
2. Propose a theoretical model that explains the relationship between the study variables based on intellectual data.
3. Examining the correlation and impact relationships between organizational integrity and symmetry to determine their levels in these sectors.
4. Identifying the dimensions of Organizational Integrity in the surveyed sectors.
5. Describe and diagnose the dimensions of organizational integrity and organizational symmetry.

To reach a set of basic and useful conclusions and recommendations that should be considered in sectors in general, based on the results.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 RESEARCH VARIABLES

2.2 ORGANIZATION INTEGRITY (INDEPENDENT VARIABLE)

Organizational Integrity is defined as a concept based on self-governance that corresponds with principles that define and give life to organizational values to create an environment that supports ethical behavior and establishes a common sense of responsibility among employees.[1] it refers to what organizations seek to achieve by ensuring strong alignment between their objectives, principles, transparency, decision-making processes, and actions throughout all levels. According to [2] it is an approach that aims to reduce organizational corruption and integrate operational systems with ethical standards. As for [3] It is a moral standard that includes responsibility, commitment, and self-governance, it's aligned with the organization's strategic policies to support value-based management and build a solid foundation for achieving organizational excellence. Moving on to [4] organizational integrity is an organizational approach that aims to leverage positive or purposeful behaviors that achieve a clear increase in the stability of organizations in an environment characterized by continuous changes in its factors. In addition, [5]stated that organizational integrity is regarded as a positive behavior that significantly enhances performance. This concept encompasses a range of constructive behaviors and values that influence the organization's dynamics. It manifests in employee actions driven by their commitment to optimism, trust, empathy, integrity, and tolerance in their interactions with others. These values foster a supportive culture throughout the organization's activities and departments. [6]went to the fact that organizational integrity is the qualities, characteristics, and culture practiced by leaders and workers in institutional work that increase a sense of pride in work, and appreciation for others, which leads to achieving organizational Symmetry. Based on the above, organizational integrity encompasses all facets of positive behavior with its ethical implications, which are disseminated among employees within the organization. It guides workers to avoid negative elements and combat corruption through organizational practices that are socially accepted. Individuals are committed to embodying qualities such as (optimism, trust, empathy, and tolerance), reflecting a culture of ethical behavior and moral virtues in personal and professional interactions. Leadership patterns will significantly influence organizational goals and work satisfaction levels. To ensure welfare and work satisfaction managers should accord people as the ultimate organizational assets [7].

2.2.1 IMPORTANCE OF ORGANIZATIONAL INTEGRITY

Organizational integrity is an essential part of ethos, where employees have to adopt and adhere to the highest ethical standards of the social system to which they belong. In this context, integrity represents adherence to ethical standards that foster social cohesion, contribute to organizational members' personal development, and enable individuals to flourish to achieve unique human goals. Integrity leads to enhanced individual performance and increased organizational efficiency.[8] Furthermore, being part of an organization that upholds ethical behaviors motivates individuals to seek personal fulfillment through good work performance, positive behaviors, financial rewards, and career advancement.[9] As ethics and social responsibility become increasingly important in organizations, integrity becomes essential for the sustainability of the organization and the well-being of individuals and society. Integrity also plays an important role in achieving key outcomes such as employee commitment, job satisfaction, intentions to change, and organizational citizenship behavior.[10] Hence, while endurance, development, and competitiveness are critical for overall organizational success and goal achievement to ensure organizations' survival, growth, and competitiveness, they are

critical to organizational performance [11]. It raises the degree of subtlety and development of feelings of belonging and trust and enables individuals to use their skills properly to meet organizational objectives. It also plays a role in enhancing organizational health and preventing extremism in actions, words, feelings, and behavior. The researchers believe that organizational Integrity seeks to provide a work environment based on professional values and ethics, such as the values of honesty, love, cooperation, constructive dialogue, and sincerity at work, which contribute to achieving distinct, cohesive relationships and lead to achieving the desired goals.

2.2.2 DIMENSIONS OF ORGANIZATIONAL INTEGRITY

2.2.2.1 OPTIMISM

Optimism is considered one of the important pillars of the positive psychology movement. It plays a major role in an individual's well-being because it impacts the individual's growth, sense of purpose, happiness, and pride in his or her work and achievements[12]. Therefore, optimistic employees are more effective, flexible, and likely to stay in a career for a sufficient period in the difficult circumstances that most organizations face in competition compared to their counterparts with pessimistic psychology[13]. Optimism contributes to a strong sense of purpose, which results in positive responses. As a result, employees expect success and perform well when faced with challenges [14]. Optimism is a personal and organizational trait that indicates belief in success regardless of immediate challenges.

2.2.2.2 EMPATHY

Empathy is a unique human trait that involves an individual's genuine concern for others and is considered a fundamental pillar of ethical living [5]. Empathy involves understanding others' emotions and considering things from their perspective. It is also important at the group level, where it promotes shared positive feelings such as satisfaction and appreciation, increases group commitment, reduces turnover rates, and increases cooperation [14]. Empathy is a moral value that has been of great importance throughout the history of societies. Empathy encompasses deep concern for others and it's a fundamental basis of ethical living [15]. It also means supporting and creating a work environment for individuals who face performance, behavioral, and psychological challenges. This indicates that empathy is employees' concern for one another.

2.2.2.3 TRUST

Trust is an optimistic expectation that is formed based on an individual's history and background. Trust relies on the anticipation that the other party will act consistently in situations that demand a high degree of trust [16].Therefore, [17]indicated that it is "a psychological experience that involves the intention to accept the actions of another person." It is based on the expectation that individuals will perform the work as expected." Trust leads to ease of dealing between individuals and an increase in the degree of cooperation and dependability among them as a result of a positive atmosphere. Trust is vital for fostering collaborative relationships in an organization, as it strengthens organizational stability and enhances member satisfaction [18].Trust, which means organizational loyalty, is subject to increase and decrease depending on the interactions between management and workers. Here, we see the social exchange theory that explains trust, as it is a set of feelings that guarantee always working in the field of good faith, with an emphasis on honesty.

2.2.2.4 TOLERANCE

Most scholars believe that Tolerance is the replacement of negative feelings with positive feelings when the affected individual chooses to abandon the feeling of resentment and bitterness towards the negative situation or situations issued by the perpetrating individual and replace them with feelings, Positive social behavior, and then it is a process of conscious choice by the individual. Therefore, the effects of Tolerance appear on employees and organizations [19]. According to[20] Tolerance involves acknowledging a genuine apology for mistakes made by an employee this kind of act helps the organization attain performance levels. it is also related to actions intended to halt or prevent negative consequences from human interactions. The concept of Tolerance is reflected in the method of pardon and forgiveness for working individuals when a type of negative behavior or failure to perform, as Integrity, cannot be guaranteed if the organization is not tolerant of its workers.

2.3 ORGANIZATIONAL SYMMETRY (DEPENDENT VARIABLE)

Organizational Symmetry is one of the recent topics discussed in the field of organization theory and organizational behavior in particular. Researchers have recently addressed it as an important variable in explaining and determining the nature of the relationship between the individual and the organization in which they work. This strong relationship goes beyond the formal and structural aspects of the organization's internal environment[21]; the presence of organizational Symmetry has become an urgent requirement in contemporary business organizations and their administrative leadership to fortify their internal structures, especially after the emergence of new values, customs, and goals about the individual and the organization, as well as facing challenges of the rapidly changing business environment and the development of its (economic, politics, and social) events. [22]and [23] shows that organizational Symmetry is the individual's emotional

awareness of their membership towards the group of individuals with whom they work in performing the same job due to the presence of behavioral compatibility among each, as well as the feeling of their membership towards the organization as a whole due to the presence of common characteristics between the individuals and the organization about values and goals, and [24] believes it is the individual's feeling that he/she is part through his/her focus and assimilation of the organization's values, which gives the organization a feeling of pride and pride in his/her membership in it. It is seen as the organization's level of broad personal integration of individuals working together. [25] refers to organizational Symmetry as the psychological relationship that links the worker to their organization through the strong feeling that this relationship generates for the individual and strengthens their commitment to the organization. In the same context, [26] indicates that organizational Symmetry is those components represented by the attraction of the organization, consistency or congruence of individual goals, loyalty, and membership. The researcher believes that Organizational Symmetry is a multi-dimensional concept that ensures achieving employee satisfaction, improving material and moral working conditions, providing fair wages and encouraging rewards, empowering employees and making them real partners in decision-making, as well as forming work teams, which contributes to strengthening the organization's competitive position in the long term.

2.3.1 IMPORTANCE OF ORGANIZATIONAL SYMMETRY

By adopting the principle of organizational Symmetry, organizations will seek to provide a positive work environment that enables them to achieve what they aspire to and which gives them the strength and effectiveness to outperform their competitors. The concept of organizational Symmetry is regarded as one of the crucial and fundamental topics in business organizations. [27] indicates that organizational Symmetry is considered a fundamental and vital factor for the work climate in the organization, as it affects the satisfaction of employees and their productive efficiency, and the most important factors for success are the existence of consensus and congruence of interests. Personality or personal goals and the goals of the organization. [28] Summarize the importance of Symmetry through the following:

1. Achieving the balance between employees in terms of power, authority, professional competence, and distribution of knowledge.
2. Determining organizational Symmetry by achieving consistency in social activities for people related to each other, as these activities can be determined through interaction in organizational structures within a specific social situation.
3. Emphasis not only on professional expertise in carrying out tasks and duties but on the social competence with which team members relate
4. Building a collaborative relationship between individual employees and customers by enabling individual employees to participate in decision-making and deal directly with the customer by sharing their observations

2.3.2 DIMENSIONS OF ORGANIZATIONAL SYMMETRY

2.3.2.1 LOYALTY

Loyalty is considered an advanced degree of satisfaction, as employees with loyalty are comfortable with their relationship with their managers and colleagues, which means they are highly satisfied with the place in which they work, which generates in them a high degree of positive feeling about their jobs and their performance in the desired manner. [29] and [30] showed that leaders in contemporary organizations can create loyalty in the hearts of their working members by caring for them, meeting their desires, and dealing with them based on respect and Appreciation in a way that enhances their functional capabilities, as well as making room for the development of their capabilities through the availability of training support, continuous and learning. [31] point out that individuals who have loyalty are in a state that makes them pledge to organizational success and believes that working there is the best option for them they are dedicated to remaining with their organization and they're not looking for Alternatives.

2.3.2.2 MEMBERSHIP

Membership is the motivation that directs the individual to the necessity of belonging to the group or organization and stems from the individual's need to be part of a group or a social unit, that is, to be accepted by the work group as one of them, surrounded by affection, attention, and cooperation. Incentives and motivation theories have dealt with the term membership because it is one of the most important motives that motivates the individual and influences his or her behavior [21]. [32] explained that membership is a person's need to consider themselves as one of the members of a group linked by common interests that motivate them to deal with each other and seek protection and assistance from one other. It is the individual's need to build associative relationships with other people, such as their colleagues, subordinates, and supervisors. It also includes the agreement of the working individuals on the organization's values and goals, and to participate in all the various work in the organization. According to [33] membership includes characteristics such as a psychological state that describes the relationship between the individual worker and the organization and the individual's connection to the organization through his keenness to continue membership in the organization.

2.3.2.3 SIMILARITY

It is an important dimension for the success of the symmetry process between the individual and the organization evidenced by the presence of a large degree of similarity between the values, goals, desires, and interests of both parties [34]. The individual may realize that they are similar to certain individuals in the group, or to the characteristics of a particular group through their similarity to the goals, Standards of Behavior, and Performance [21]. The similarity between individuals and organizational goals unleashes the occurrence of loyalty, which creates a sense of belonging and membership, this is what embodies the state of similarity, and it is observed when the goals of the group are identical to the organization’s goals, this group is more productive [35]. In the same context, Organizational Symmetry is defined as the extent to which employees in the organization feel that they are an integral part of it, which stimulates in them a sense of citizenship to survive their organizations, comply with their orders, enhance their values, reflect their ideas, and defend them against any external threat because the threat is trying to destabilize its stability, future directions, and sense of pride, belonging, and loyalty. As individuals realize that there is an overlap between the characteristics of the organization and their characteristics, they become psychologically attached to their organizations and see their identity During it [36].

3 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study framework included both quantitative and qualitative research methods. The collected data was from a questionnaire form that was distributed and filled with 144 respondents as a Google form design using a probability sampling method. The questionnaire of this study included three parts; the first part was about demographic questions, which contained (Gender, Age, Levels of Certificates, Years of Experience, and Organization status). In the second part, researchers wanted to know the respondent's opinion about whether they think that Organizational Integrity impacts Organizational Symmetry or not before they answered the main part of the research study, which was the third part as a (Yes/No) type. In the end, the third part of the questionnaire includes some questions as a Likert-scale type (Strongly Disagree=1, Disagree=2, Neutral=3, Agree=4 and Strongly Agree=5), which represented the independent and dependent variables of our study research [37].

3.1 STUDY MODEL

To complete the treatment of the study’s problem and achieve its objectives, the hypothesis of the study was built as shown in the following figure:

FIGURE 1: Study Model

3.2 HYPOTHESIS OF STUDY

First main hypothesis: There is a significant correlation between Organizational Integrity and Organizational Symmetry, and the following sub-hypotheses are derived from it:

H₁: There is a strong positive correlation between the Optimism dimension and Organizational Symmetry (Loyalty, Similarity, and Membership).

H₂: There is a strong positive correlation between the Empathy dimension and Organizational Symmetry (Loyalty, Similarity, and Membership).

H₃: There is a strong positive correlation between the Trust dimension and Organizational Symmetry (Loyalty, Similarity, and Membership).

H₄: There is a strong positive correlation between the Tolerance dimension and Organizational Symmetry (Loyalty, Similarity, and Membership).

Second main hypothesis: There is a statistically significant effect of Organizational Integrity on Organizational Symmetry, and the following sub-hypotheses emerge from it:

H₅: There is a statistically significant effect of Organizational Integrity on Organizational Symmetry (Loyalty dimension).

H₆: There is a statistically significant impact of Organizational Integrity on Organizational Symmetry (Similarity dimension).

H₇: There is a statistically significant effect of Organizational Integrity on Organizational Symmetry (Membership dimension).

H₈: There is a statistically significant relationship between variables.

3.3 STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Statistical analysis is a critical tool in research and decision-making, allowing analysts to make sense of complex data and draw meaningful conclusions that inform actions and strategies. It relies on mathematical principles and statistical software to perform a wide range of data-related tasks. The two types of statistical analysis is descriptive and inferential statistics.

3.3.1 RELIABILITY TEST

Reliability Test refers to the degree to which a test is consistent and stable in measuring what it is intended to measure. Most put, a test is reliable if it is consistent within itself and across time. Internal consistency of the characteristics describing these factors was verified using the Cronbach Alpha coefficient [38]. The results allowed us to calculate Cronbach's Coefficient Alpha, which measures how well the grouped statements match each selected audience perception feature. Cronbach's alpha can have values anywhere from $-\infty$ to 1, but only positive values make sense. A coefficient value around one indicates more reliability [39, 40] "see table 1".

3.3.2 TABLES

Table 1. Reliability statistics for all constructs

Variables	No. of Items	Alpha Cronbach
Optimism	4	0.77
Empathy	4	0.66
Trust	4	0.65
Tolerance	4	0.77
All IDVs	16	0.87
Loyalty	4	0.65
Similarity	4	0.72
Membership	4	0.69
All D.V.s	12	0.82
IDVs and D.V.s	28	0.90

In Table 1, we can see the summary of the reliability test for our research study that clarifies Cronbach's alpha (α) values for all constructs. results showed that the research independent variables (Optimism, Empathy, Trust, and Tolerance) with four items ($\alpha = 0.77, 0.66, 0.65,$ and 0.77) were reliable. Similarly, the three dependent variables (Loyalty, Similarity, and Membership) scales, each with four items ($\alpha = 0.65, 0.72,$ and 0.69) respectively, were found reliable. As we noticed in the table above, all independent variables with 16 items ($\alpha = 0.87$) and all dependent variables with 12 items ($\alpha = 0.82$) were also found reliable, and finally, reliability was assessed for all independent and all dependent variables with 28 items ($\alpha = 0.90$) were also found reliable.

3.3.3 STATISTICAL INSTRUMENTS

It is used to collect, analyze, interpret, and present data in a systematic and meaningful way. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize and present data, including measures like frequency and percentages for demographic questions [39]. Also, researchers used two types of inferential analysis, the Chi-Square Test of Independence (χ^2) and the correlation and regression method, to show the relationship between variables. Data were analyzed using SPSS V.26.

3.3.3.1 CHI-SQUARE TEST OF INDEPENDENCE (χ^2)

The chi-square test is used to determine whether there is a statistically significant association between the expected frequencies and the observed frequencies in one or more categories of a contingency table [41-43]. The

frequency of each category for one nominal variable is compared across the categories of the second nominal variable. This test is also known as the Chi-Square Test of Association [44]. The critical value for the chi-square statistic is determined by the level of significance, typically $\alpha = .05$, and the degrees of freedom for the chi-square, and degree of freedom ($df = (r-1)(c-1)$) where r is the number of rows and c is the number of columns. This test utilizes a contingency table to analyze the data [37, 45, 46]. The value of the Chi-Square Test of the Independence:

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{i=1}^r \sum_{j=1}^c \frac{(O_{ij} - E_{ij})^2}{E_{ij}} \quad (1)$$

Where

$$\chi^2 = \text{Chi - Square of Independence.} \quad (2)$$

$$O_{ij} = \text{Observed value of two nominal variables.} \quad (3)$$

$$E_{ij} = \text{expected value of two nominal variables.} \quad (4)$$

3.3.3.2 CORRELATION AND REGRESSION ANALYSIS

It is used in statistics to describe the pattern or relationship between independent variables and three dependent variables [47, 48]. If they move in the same direction, the correlation is positive; if they move in opposite directions, the correlation is negative, and Correlation coefficients go from -1 (perfect negative correlation) to $+1$ (perfect positive correlation), while 0 indicates no correlation [49].

Regression analysis is used to find the impact of independent variables on dependent variable. Multiple Linear Regression was used to identify the predictor (independent) variables, including (Optimism et al. and Tolerance) that predict each of the response (Dependent) variables (Loyalty, Similarity, and Membership) [50, 51].

3.3.4 STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

First of all, researchers used descriptive statistics, which can help in summarizing data in the form of simple quantitative measures such as percentages or means [52].

As we see in Table 2, a chi-square test of Independence was performed to examine the relationship between demographic variables and respondents' opinions about how Organizational Integrity affected Organizational Symmetry. In the above table, statistical analysis revealed that with a p-value of (0.077, 0.606, 0.247, 0.393, and 0.142) greater than the significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$, the hypothesis (H_8) can be rejected with a confidence of 95 percent. It can be, thus, concluded that there is strong evidence of a correlational relationship involving demographic variables and respondents' opinions about how Organizational Integrity affected Organizational Symmetry.

In this part of the research, researchers tried to demonstrate the Correlation analysis to show the relationship between variables and analyze the hypothesis, and they employed the multiple linear regression analysis at 95% confidence intervals.

In Table 3, spearman's rank-order correlation was run to examine the relationship between levels of independent variables (Optimism, Empathy, Trust, and Tolerance) and dependent variables (Loyalty, Similarity, and Membership). From the above table, we can see that there were positive and significant correlations between Optimism and (Loyalty, Similarity, and Membership) with $R_s = (0.40, 0.26, \text{ and } 0.42)$ respectively, $n=144$, $p<0.001$, Trust and (Loyalty, Similarity, and Membership) with $R_s = (0.44, 0.28, \text{ and } 0.39)$ respectively, $n=144$, $p<0.00$. In addition, we noticed that there were positive and significant correlations between Empathy and (Loyalty, Similarity, and Membership) with $R_s = (0.55, 0.42, \text{ and } 0.54)$ respectively, $n=144$, $p<0.001$, and finally, Tolerance and (Loyalty, Similarity, and Membership) with $R_s = (0.50, 0.31, \text{ and } 0.54)$ respectively, $n=144$, $p<0.00$. For this purpose, we can accept all hypotheses ($H_1, H_2, H_3, \text{ and } H_4$).

In Table 4, a stepwise regression was run to predict loyalty levels from (Optimism, Trust, Empathy, and Tolerance). This resulted in a significant model, ($F = 49.955, p < .001, R^2 = 0.415$), so we can accept the hypothesis H_5 . The individual predictors were examined further and indicated that Empathy ($t = 5.290, p < .001$), and Tolerance ($t = 3.653, p < .001$) were significant predictors.

Table 2. Relationships between Demographic Questions and if Organizational Integrity has Effect on Organizational Symmetry (Y) - using Chi-Square Test

Demographic Questions		Y		Total	Chi-Square Value	P-Value
		Yes	No			
Gender	Male	80	8	88	3.117	0.077
	Female	55	1	56		
	Total	135	9	144		
Age	Below 25 years	6	1	7	1.841	0.606
	25 – 30 years	42	3	45		
	31 – 35 years	49	4	53		
	35 and above	38	1	39		
	Total	135	9	144		
Years of Experience	Below five years	6	1	7	4.142	0.247
	5 -10 years	42	5	47		
	11 – 15 years	21	0	21		
	Above 15 years	66	3	69		
	Total	135	9	144		
Certificate Level	Diploma	25	2	27	4.098	0.393
	Bachelors	49	4	53		
	Master	37	2	39		
	PhD	21	0	21		
	Other	3	1	4		
	Total	135	9	144		
Organization Status	Employee	45	1	46	5.442	0.142
	Manager	11	2	13		
	Teacher	60	3	63		
	Other	19	3	22		
	Total	135	9	144		

Table 3. Correlation matrix between independent variables and dependent variables

Independent Variables	Dependent Variables		
	Loyalty	Membership	Similarity
Optimism	0.402**	0.255**	0.419**
Trust	0.439**	0.275**	0.385**
Empathy	0.546**	0.418**	0.538**
Tolerance	0.492**	0.311**	0.544**

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4. Impact of each of the independent variable (Optimism, Empathy, Trust, and Tolerance) on Dependent Variable (Loyalty) using Stepwise Regression

	Coefficients			Model Summary		ANOVA	
	Beta coefficient	t-value	P-value	Correlation	R Square	F	p-value
(Constant)	1.011	3.616	0.000				
Empathy	0.486	5.290	0.000	0.644	0.415	49.955	0.000
Tolerance	0.281	3.653	0.000				

Table 5. Impact of each of the independent variable (Optimism, Empathy, Trust, and Tolerance) on Dependent Variable (Similarity) using Stepwise Regression

	Coefficients			Model Summary		ANOVA	
	Beta coefficient	t-value	P-value	Correlation	R Square	F	p-value
(Constant)	1.393	5.426	0.000	0.641	0.410	49.088	0.000
Tolerance	0.398	5.647	0.000				
Empathy	0.267	3.168	0.002				

As Table 5 shows, a stepwise regression was run to predict the similarity level from (Optimism, Trust, Empathy, and Tolerance). This resulted in a significant model, ($F = 49.088, p < .001, R^2 = 0.410$), this means we can accept the hypothesis H_6 . The individual predictors were examined further and indicated that both Empathy ($t = 3.168, p < .001$) and Tolerance ($t = 5.647, p < .001$) were significant predictors.

Table 6. Impact of each of the independent variable (Optimism, Empathy, Trust, and Tolerance) on Dependent Variable (Membership) using Stepwise Regression

	Coefficients			Model Summary		ANOVA	
	Beta coefficient	t-value	P-value	Correlation	R Square	F	p-value
(Constant)	2.610	9.581	0.000				
Tolerance	0.407	5.519	0.000	0.420	0.177	30.459	0.000

In Table 6, a stepwise regression was run to predict membership level from (Optimism, Trust, Empathy, and Tolerance). This resulted in a significant model, ($F = 30.459, p < .001, R^2 = 0.177$), so we can accept the hypothesis H_7 . The individual predictors were examined further and indicated that only Tolerance ($t = 5.519, p < .001$) was a significant predictor.

4 RESULT DESCUSSION

This research study focused on the significant effect of Organizational Integrity on Organizational Symmetry. Accordingly, our findings supported that there is strong evidence of an association relationship between demographic variables and respondents' opinions about how Organizational Integrity affected Organizational Symmetry. Also, there is a positive and significant correlation between Organizational Integrity with four levels (Optimism, Empathy, Trust, and Tolerance) and Organizational Symmetry with three levels (Loyalty, Similarity, and Membership). In addition, we found that there is a statistically significant effect of Organizational Integrity (Empathy and Tolerance) on Organizational Symmetry dimensions (Loyalty and Similarity), and only Tolerance has a statistically significant effect on (Membership) from Organizational Symmetry.

CONCUSION

1. The results of the statistical analysis showed that there is a significant correlational relationship between Organizational Integrity and Organizational Symmetry dimensions (combined) in the public and private sectors. This shows that the more top managers and employees apply and depend on the dimensions of Organizational Integrity in the investigated public and private sectors, the greater their capabilities in achieving Organizational Symmetry.
2. Statistical effect analysis of organizational Integrity on the organizational Symmetry in the researched private and public sectors was significant, that achieving individuals (Loyalty, Similarity, and Membership) of these sectors derives its ingredients for their achievement from the possession of the dimensions (Optimism, Empathy, Trust, and Tolerance) by their individuals.
3. Empathy and Tolerance dimensions of organizational Integrity achieved the highest correlation and impact relationship with both Loyalty and Similarity dimensions of organizational Symmetry in the public and private sectors, which means the Integrity between individuals, goes back to their Empathy and Tolerance for each other, which creates a sense of similarity, and loyalty to their sectors. On the other hand, also Tolerance has a significant impact on Membership dimension of organizational Symmetry.
4. Trust and optimism dimensions of organizational Integrity were not significant predictors of organizational Symmetry and achieved a low level of correlation, which indicates that individuals in private and public sectors are not optimistic and trustworthy of their sectors, and their Integrity goes back to Empathy and Tolerance.

RECOMMENDATION

1. Private and public sectors should be more transparent and announce the sector's situation and information to their employees. This leads to trust and honesty, which will ease the dealing between individuals and increase the degree of cooperation and dependability among them in cooperative relationships. This enhances organization stability and members' satisfaction, and that will create loyalty, membership, and similarity (organizational Symmetry).
2. Private and public sector administrators must create a positive atmosphere, and it is linked with trust, which is necessary for employees' Optimism towards their sectors (organization). Optimism is a personal trait that indicates belief in success regardless of immediate challenges. That kind of Optimism needs trust and honesty, which leads to a positive expectation that the other party will behave similarly in a comparable situation, which leads to similarity, which is one of the dimensions of organizational identity.
3. It is necessary for private and public administrators to depend on organizational integrity principles and dimensions to face corruption, what the researchers in other studies insisted on and proved, what will create organizational Symmetry in the end.
4. Although it is wise to recommend that employee empowerment and autonomy should be priorities in a business, the researchers would like to point out that some gaps are not considered in this paper, such as the sociological and psychological aspects of the topic.
5. The researchers also believe that a cross-cultural analysis should be done following a cultural analysis of several cultures to be able to understand better, how the context may affect the results of this study.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The author declares no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data of this study are kept by the corresponding author and will be available to you in case of need.

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